

**MODELLING OF BUSINESS EDUCATORS' PERCEIVED IMPACT OF CASHLESS POLICY
ADOPTION ON DIGITAL SMES PERFORMANCE IN NORTH-EAST, NIGERIA**

Lukman Suleiman¹, Wasilu Suleiman², Buhari Suleiman³, and Umar Buba⁴

^{1&4}Department of Vocational and Technology Education Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi

^{1&2}Department of Business Administration Bauchi State University Gadau

Corresponding email: luckmansuleiman@gmail.com

+2347037714353

Abstract

This research is aimed at investigating the Modelling of Business Educators' Perceived Impact of Cashless Policy Adoption on Digital SMEs Performance in North-East, Nigeria. The study employs a survey research design. A maximum of 208 questionnaires was administered to the business education lecturers in the universities in the North-Eastern Nigeria. Smart PLS-SEM version 4.0 was employed for data analysis in this study. The tool was used to assess and evaluate the statistical significance of relevant path coefficients of the study variables. The results of this study disclosed that cashless policy could positively enhance digital SMEs performance. The results also indicates that digital SMEs owners could easily adapt to cashless policy in Nigeria. Thus, the use of cashless policy that has persistently remained discouraging over the years especially in digital SMEs can significantly be used and enhanced. The study recommends that future research needs to capitalize on perceptions of producers, sellers as well as customers that are directly involved in digital SMEs. Furthermore, this study also highlighted that future studies should examine the possibility of using technology awareness as either mediating or moderating variable.

Keywords: Digital SMEs, Cashless Policy and Business Educators

Introduction

Small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) are considered to be the backbone of any economy in the world today. It has become imperative for business experts to monitor and determine the performance of digital SMEs for viable economy. Cicea, Popa, Marinescu, and Ștefan (2019) uncovered that the importance of studying digital SMEs performance stems from several salient aspects. Cicea, Popa, Marinescu, and Ștefan (2019) further reiterates that digital SMEs have a significant influence on both unemployment and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of every nation, Practically, digital SMEs are economic system that is rapidly changes the overdependence on public sector in both national and global economies (Kiyabo & Isaga, 2020). However, this study aimed at determining perceived cashless policy adoption model of business educators on digital SMEs Performance Furthermore, Prasanna et al. (2019) said that digital SMEs' performance is the outcomes of application of technological gadgets in firms' business activities, it can be measured through the use many indicators. Thus, firms' growth and ease of doing business are among important indicators of digital SMEs' performance measures (Bouwmana, Nikoub, & Reuvera,

2019). Prasanna et al. (2019), emphasizes the need for peoples' participation in the technological ways of SMEs by looking at a dynamic trends of international setting and the role that multilateral trading system can play in encouraging more dynamic cashless and inclusive digital SMEs participation in the global market.

Advancement in technology have made the business environment of today witness rapid changes, many businesses of today carry out their activities electronically through the use of cashless transactions. Abomeh and Obaide (2022) added that a cashless economy is a one whereby debit cards, credit cards, charge cards, and direct transfer of fund are being used for making transactions. Some benefits of a cashless policy in business environment is that it reduces money laundering and other cash related crimes to a minimum (Alao & Sorinola, 2015). Many developed countries such as Norway, Denmark, United Kingdom, Sweden, and many others have adopted a modernized means of cashless transactions. In Nigeria cashless policy was since adopted on June, 2012 but partially implemented. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has been at the forefront of steering the new cashless practice in Nigeria as a means to enhance security and efficacy of business transactions. In recent times the CBN has been engaged in series of reforms aimed at making the Nigerian financial sector formidable and ensuring the overall economic performance of Nigeria to align with global best practices (Abomeh & Obaide, 2022). The main objective of the cashless policy is to lessen the physical cash volume in the economy while boosting the volume of electronic-based transactions in the country (CBN, 2012). The main purpose is to encourage the payments for business transaction through electronic means.

The federal government of Nigeria insisted that electronic means of making transactions (cashless) must be implemented at least 70% in January 2023 because the policy has been recognized to have much relevance on the monetary policy, financial stability and overall economic growth of the country. According to CBN (2022) the reason for the adoption of cashless policy is to overcome the problem associated with: 1. amount of money paid for the production of hard naira note, 2. risk attached with the cost of banking services, 3. mitigate the level of social vices of kidnappers that are requesting for huge amount of money as ransom and 4. Improve the effectiveness of monetary policy in managing inflation and driving Nigerian economic growth. However, business educators are expertise that acquire the relevant skills and training needed for becoming self-employed in different areas that are associated with digital SMEs performance.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this research is to:

- i. Determine the perception of business educators on whether cashless policy could enhance digital SMEs performance in North-East, Nigeria
- ii. Examine the perception of business educators on whether digital SMEs owners could easily adapt to cashless policy in North-East, Nigeria

Literature Review

Digital SMEs Performance

Digital SMEs performance are considered as a diverse nature regarding business size, phase of maturity, and business ownership (Bouwmana et al., 2019; Ulas, 2019; Xu & Li, 2019). Digital SMEs performance are

painstaking the driving force of e-business of many economies, responsible for innovation, growth and employment opportunities (Prasanna et al., 2019).

SMEs’ performance can vividly be understood quantitatively by taking cognizance of workers’ efficiency, production level, financial results and number of customers (Kiyabo & Isaga, 2020). Additionally, Cicea et al. (2019) emphasizes that profitability, market share, productivity, dynamics of revenues, liquidity and costs are all determinants of SMEs performance. The qualitative perspective of SMEs performance on the other side involves: leadership style, goals achievement, employee behaviour, customer satisfaction product and process innovation and organizational and marketing innovation (Dauda et al., 2022).

Dbal and Cloutier (2019) identified a number of 14 indicators to describe SMEs performance, the indicators are: SMEs’ reputation, employee satisfaction, productivity, sufficient working capital, sales, profits, prompt order delivery, effectiveness in operations and production, product quality, goals achievements, number of clients, reduction in product cost, easiness in supervision, and product diversification.

Prasanna et al. (2019) said that it is also relevant to mention research that focused on the factors that influence the performance of digital SMEs. Firms must effectively combine and deploy their human, physical and organizational assets in order to survive and succeed in a potentially or existing business environment (Demirbag, Koh, Tatoglu, & Zaim, 2006). Therefore, need to develop long-term competitive strategies and, in turn achieve superior performance and advantages (Garzoni, Turi, Secundo, & Vecchio, 2019). Conversely, to mitigate the problem of limited resources, SMEs owners need to and identify other means of enhancing their competitiveness and performance.

Strategies for Digital SMEs Performance

Digital SMEs is an overall integration of information technology driven tools into SMEs business (Becker & Schmid, 2020). Crupi et al. (2020) asserts that there are numbers of strategies that could enhance the performance of digital SMEs. Digital business strategy enhances profitability and performance when it includes competition related activities to offer digital products and services (Dauda et al., 2022; Dba & Cloutier, 2019). Digital SMEs could ensure future survival in terms formulating a viable digital transformation framework that suits the business. Depaoli, Za, and Scornavacca (2020) develop framework that for successful digital SMEs performance. They emphasized that regardless of the company or industry such framework could have help SMEs in the use of technologies in business, value creation, structural adaptations and financial dimensions

Figure 1. Framework for Digital SMEs Performance

Garzoni et al. (2019) pointed out that to develop a digital strategy, firms must first identify the strategic role of new adapted IT and be able to exploit it. In particular, it is crucial whether business concerns make use of existing technology on whether they act as market leaders through their own creation of new technology. Sharing a similar view, North, Aramburu, and Lorenzo (2018) and Priyono, Moin, and Putri (2020) conclude that firms of all sizes including SMEs have to understand and practice the role of new digital technologies, as these can disruptively change the existing business model. Additionally, the new digital technologies in SMEs result in new business opportunities and sometimes threats for other small businesses (Pradhan, 2018; Ramdani, Raja, & Kayumova, 2021).

Technological adaptations in SMEs have an impact on the entire value chain of businesses that might often leads to extent of changes in the added value creation to which new digital SMEs activities deviate from the typical analogue business that is practicable by many business owners (Schönfuß et al., 2021). Integration of digital technology in SMEs for value creation requires an appropriate organizational structure in the business to successfully implement the challenges of the digital transformation and the associated tasks (Thaha, Maulina, Muftiadi, & Alexandri, 2021). The entire business design must be adapted to the circumstances by optimally integrating the new digital activities within the business structures and their influence on processes, products or skills of a firm.

Cashless Policy and the Digital SMEs

Digital SMEs have been given many different definitions by different school of thoughts (Abomeh & Obaide, 2022; Ailemen, Enobong, Osuma, Evbuomwan, & Ndigwe, 2018; Alao & Sorinola, 2015). Nevertheless, in all these scholastic views, it is largely believed that digital SMEs is the driver of economic growth especially in developing economies like Nigeria. The digital SMEs contribute enormously in local capital formation which encourages productivity in promoting the living standard of the citizens (Ayoola, 2013; Taiwo, Oluwafemi, Evawere, & Agwu, 2020). Additionally, Abomeh and Obaide (2022) asserts that SMEs plays a vital role in employment generation, Gross Domestic Products (GDP), competitive market pressure and export earnings, as well as restructuring of large enterprises in downsizing and privatization. Nonetheless, factors such as poor management, poor policy implementation, inadequate information. poor capital outlay, lack of continuity, lack of raw materials, unstable policy environmental influence, poor accounting system, poor marketing strategy, lack of market knowledge, higher interest rates and lack of technical know-how have been identified to often lead to the failure of digital SMEs (Omotunde, Sunday, & John-Dewole, 2013). Consequently, taking cognizance of the importance of the digital SMEs to the Nigerian economy, it is imperative to consider the impact of cashless on digital SMEs business and their contribution to the nation's GDP. Yaqub, Bello, Adenuga, and Ogundeji (2013) contends that the electronic currency which is the bane of cashless economy is interconnected to bank accounts and that many SME operators have no access to such and also often doesn't know how to operate the related technologies in making transactions. Following the same trend, Ailemen et al. (2018) confirms that the lack of technological knowhow in Nigeria particularly in rural areas have made electronic transaction not easy in many instances and therefore might hinder the extent of cashless policy implementation. Furthermore, Abomeh and Obaide (2022) emphasizes that increase in the overhead cost of running digital SMEs business as the impact of the cashless policy may have more impact on digital SMEs due to their limited capital outlay. Despite the 0.5% the banks charge as commission on turnover, the cashless policy has introduced an additional charge if one

uses the POS for sales. Every transaction made that exceed maximum limit either through the use of checks or POS terminals attracts a charge of 5% of the amount withdrawn. This charge does not take into account the losses incurred by the SMEs business that might likely lead to business failure. Taiwo et al. (2020) added that the role of the SMEs in providing employment opportunities may be hampered by the cashless policy since there will not be standard networking services in most of the rural areas, thereby leading to higher unemployment rate in the country. Besides, transaction channels are sometimes often made ineffective by faulty which can lead to breach in commercial transactions that might lead to multiple payments, thereby threatening funds security in digital SMEs business. Therefore, taking cognizance of the arguments for and against, great attention should be given for cashless policy in Nigeria for its impacts and contributions on enhancing economic growth and development specifically on the digital SMEs businesses.

Business Educators as a Cross-Roads for Digital SMEs

Business education is an area of study that equip its recipients with requisite knowledge, skills and attitude needed for self-reliant (Bratianu, Hadad, & Bejinaru, 2020). Additionally, business education model was designed for a steady state business environment for preparing business educators for future jobs (Andersson & Öhman, 2015). Globalization and innovativeness has significantly contributed to a dramatic change in the needs for business educators in digital SMEs for effective customers' satisfaction (Buba, Suleiman, Adamu, & Idris, 2020). Consequently, Krishnamurthy (2020) posits that universities should prepare business educators for technologies that have not yet been invented, for jobs that have not yet been created and also to solve problems that have not yet been expected. Thus, business educators could incorporate all these technological ideas into its philosophy and overcome the inertial forces of digital SMEs. Suleiman, Buba, Sabo, Idris, and Jibrin (2020) unveils that universities should open their learning environment towards creating a diverse digital universe of knowledge to stimulate and incorporating digital SMEs through internship for business educators.

Methodology

This study employs a survey research design the population of this study comprises of 475 business education lectures of universities in the North-Eastern Nigeria, 208 business education lectures were selected based on the stratified random sampling techniques. Four point Likert scale questionnaires were administered to the respondents using both face to face and online methods. The questionnaires that were filed and returned for analysis are 124. Validity and reliability of the instruments were ensured (See table 1 & table 2) below respectively. Data for the study were collected by the researcher with the help of two trained research assistants and data analysis methods was based on Structural Equation Modeling using Smart PLS version 4.0. If the statistical value of P is < 0.05 confidence level the research objectives would be supported but if they are found to be ≥ 0.5 confidence level the research objectives would not be supported. Based on prior empirical studies, the following research model was developed.

Figure 2: Research Model

To ensure validity and reliability of the instruments, this study uses the cumulative items of Average variance Extracted (AVE), Composite Reliability (CR) and Cronbach Alpha values obtained from assessment of measurement model in smart PLS-SEM as in table 1 and discriminant validity in table 2 below respectively in order to ascertain whether the variables of the study have reach the recommended threshold of ≥ 0.70 and or ≥ 0.50 before the variables could be considered reliable (Hair, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2013). Additionally, A1, A2, A3, A4, B2, B3, B4, B5, B6, C1, C2, C3, C4 and C5 are the items of the research questionnaire, they were used because of the strength of their factor loadings above 0.5. Item A5, B1 and C6 were deleted from the model because they have low factor loadings and these could affect validity and reliability of the research instruments (Hair, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2013).

Table 1: Reliability of the Instruments

Items	AVE	CR	Crunbach's Alpha
Cashless Enhancement	0.673	0.845	0.838
Policy Adaptation	0.597	0.850	0.827
Digital SMEs	0.665	0.875	0.872

Table 2: Discriminant Validity

Items	Cashless Enhancement	Digital SMEs	Policy Adaptation
Cashless Enhancement			
Digital SMEs	0.694		
Policy Adaptation	0.528	0.980	

In this study, all the values for AVE, CR, Cronbach Alpha and discriminant validity are above the recommended threshold values of > 0.7, and/or > 0.5 on their respective variables. Moreover, table 2 above also indicate discriminant validity values > 0.7, and/or > 0.5. Therefore, the questionnaire items are valid and reliable.

Results

The research objective one was formulated to determine the perception of business educators on whether cashless policy could enhance digital SMEs performance in North-East, Nigeria. Consequently, the result of the PLS-SEM structural model unveiled that the path coefficient value which shows the strength of perception for business educators on whether cashless policy could enhance digital SMEs performance was 0.273 and P value was 0.000 and the T values was 7.83. Therefore, the T values for such perception exceeded 1.96 at 0.05 confidence levels using two tail tests rule of thumb. In essence, the results show that cashless policy could enhance digital SMEs performance as indicated in table 3 and figure 3 below.

Table 3: PLS-SEM Path Coefficient Model Result of Perceived Cashless Policy and Digital SMEs Performance

Items	Path Coefficients	T Values	P Values
Cashless Enhancement.-> Digital SMEs	0.273	7.283	0.000

Source: Field survey

Note: **p< 0.05

Figure 3: Statistical Analysis of the Research Model

Figure 4: Graphical Representation of Cashless Enhancement and Digital SMEs

Figure 4 above indicated a normality of the distribution, this indicates and further interpreted the result of table 3 above which indicates that cashless policy could enhance digital SMEs performance in Nigeria. Therefore, the first research objective of this study explains that there is need for government to enhance and improve the use of cashless policy for the betterment of digital SMEs performance in Nigeria.

The research objective two was developed to examine the perception of business educators on whether digital SMEs owners could easily adapt to cashless policy in North-East, Nigeria. Subsequently, the findings from PLS-SEM structural model revealed that the path coefficient value which shows the strength of perception for business educators’ on whether digital SMEs owners could easily adapt to cashless policy was 0.719 and P value was 0.000 and the T values was 20.003. Consequently, the T values for such perception exceeded 1.96 at 0.05 confidence levels using two tail tests rule of thumb. In essence, the results indicate that digital SMEs owners could easily adapt to cashless policy as shown in table 4 and figure 5 below.

Table 4: PLS-SEM Path Coefficient Model Result of Perceived Cashless Policy and SMEs Performance

Items	Path Coefficients	T Values	P Values
Cashless Policy Adaption-> Digital SMEs	0.719	20.003	0.000

Source: Field survey

Note: ** $p < 0.05$

Figure 5: Graphical Representation of Cashless policy and Digital SMEs performance

The graph above also indicated a normality of the distribution, this interpreted and further indicates the result displayed on table 4 above which shows that digital SMEs owners could easily adapt to cashless policy in Nigeria. Therefore, the second research objective of this study highlighted the need for orienting digital SMEs owners about cashless transactions so that digital SMEs could be enhanced in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of research objective one indicated the perception of business educators where cashless policy could effectively enhance digital SMEs performance. This finding is in harmony with (Kiyabo & Isaga, 2020) who reported that cashless policy is effective for small, medium and large scale enterprises. Similarly, another finding was identified in the work of (Alao & Sorinola, 2015) on the performance of SMEs using hard currencies the findings unveils that online transactions is more effective in SMEs transactions in comparism with buying and selling using hard currencies. This finding is however in concord with the findings of research objective two of this study which uncovers that digital SMEs owners could easily adapt to cashless policy.

Conclusion

The findings of this study suggest that cashless policy could enhance digital SMEs performance and that digital SMEs owners could easily adapt to cashless policy in Nigeria. Therefore, the use of cashless policy that has persistently remained discouraging over the years especially in digital SMEs can significantly be used and enhanced.

Recommendation

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study

- i. Digital SMEs should embrace the use cashless transactions for their day to day businesses as this could enhance performance
- ii. Government should intervene in providing stable networks providers for digital SMEs owners so that could easily adapt to changes related to cashless policy

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